

SHOULDER WEAR SIMULATOR FOR INVESTIGATION OF WEAR OF GLENOID COMPONENT

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SUMMARY: Wear of polyethylene glenoid component is one of main complications in total shoulder arthroplasty. Glenoid component wear can be the result of not properly selected materials for articular surfaces. Therefore, wear of glenoid component should be evaluated in vitro to select a proper material for load-bearing application. Several studies have been done for wear testing of total hip and knee replacements. However, no experimental wear study has been performed to investigate influence of the component material and geometry on wear performance of glenoid prosthesis yet. The aim of the study is to develop a shoulder wear simulator, which will be used for wear testing of the currently used and alternative glenoid components.

Wear testing device is developed to simulate the abduction/adduction movement of the shoulder joint. During the movement a physiologically-correct loading will be applied to the prosthetic components. The humeral head abduction/adduction movement is realized by stepper-motor. The axial loading is realized by force controlled pneumatic actuator. The movement and loading are computer controlled. The glenoid component is mounted in the special holder. The humeral head is mounted on the rotated axis. A new born calf serum is used as a lubricant. The lubricant temperature is maintained at 37°C using thermocouple. Wear of the glenoid component is measured gravimetrically according to ASTM standard. The shoulder wear simulator allows also for obtaining the friction factor between articulated prosthetic materials during the wear test.

Before using the device for actual material testing, initial preliminary tests were done to ensure that the device was operating properly under test condition. Good repeatability and accuracy performances of the motor and cylinder have been found. Then, the preliminary wear test for polyethylene glenoid component and metal humeral was performed. The test ran for 2 millions cycles under loads, which changed from 150N to 750N during each cycle. After the test was completed, the glenoid component was inspected for wear. The calculated volumetric wear rate was of about 40 mm³/yr. The maximum wear depth was of about 0.2 mm.

This test method is developed for in vitro evaluating the friction and wear properties of combinations materials that are being considered for use as the bearing surfaces of human joint replacement under physiological load/motion/lubrication conditions. Flexibility of the device allows programming of many different motion and loading configurations. Through the preliminary wear test, the device proved effectiveness at reproducing the desired motions and loads, and initiating wear.

KEYWORDS: wear, shoulder simulator, prostheses, UHMWPE

1. INTRODUCTION

Polyethylene (PE) wear and loosening of glenoid component are the main factors increasing complication rate in total shoulder arthroplasty [1,7]. In studies of retrieved glenoid components [5], abrasion, burnishing, pitting and delamination were found the most predominant modes of polyethylene wear. Therefore, surface wear and subsurface fatigue mechanisms might contribute to glenoid implant failure. Moreover, in contrast to acetabular or tibial components, the small thickness of the glenoid component (typically less than 7 mm), and less joint conformity (gleno-humeral radial clearance ranging from 1 to 5mm)

might result in higher contact stresses, and thus in a higher wear rate. PE wear debris can provoke an foreign-body reaction which induces a bone resorption around the implant and can cause periprosthetic osteolysis resulting, over the time, in glenoid component loosening [8,12]. In addition to loosening, the stabilising function of the glenoid component can be disturbed by deformation (cold flow) and damage of the polyethylene glenoid prosthesis. It was found that glenohumeral instability after arthroplasty was associated with loss of the glenoid rim [7]. It can be concluded that it is important to predict the amount of wear in different types of glenoid components and to identify design configurations, which will show the lower incidence of wear-related failure of the implant.

The wear and deformation of polyethylene depend mainly on the geometries of prostheses, loading, motion and lubrication condition. Other factors affecting the wear include the material factors (material properties, manufacturing process, sterilization method and atmospheric exposure that can lead to oxidative degradation), patient factors (weight, activity and bone properties) and surgical factors (positioning and fixation method). To investigate the *in vitro* tribological wear performance of the human joint replacement several experimental studies [3, 4] have been done using joint wear simulators. However, in the wide range of tribological human joint testers being in use, no shoulder wear simulator has been developed and no experimental *in vitro* wear study has been reported investigating wear performance of shoulder prosthesis yet.

The aim of this study is to develop a shoulder wear simulator based on the anatomy and biomechanics of shoulder joint and the standardized methods of wear assessment. The wear simulator will be used to assess *in vitro* wear performance of the currently used all-polyethylene glenoid component.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Shoulder wear simulator

The design criteria for shoulder wear simulator have been established based upon the anatomy and biomechanics of human shoulder joint. Because simulation of complex, 3D joint movements would be too complicated, thus too expensive, only abduction/adduction movement until 90° will be simulated in the test. The abduction movement was chosen for simulation, because during the abduction the highest glenohumeral joint forces occur, thus more wear is expected than during another joint movements. Test load profile is representative of that which occurs during patient's abduction movements with peak loads equal to 750N (Figure 1).

Schematic and realistic overviews of the developed simulator have been shown in Figure 2 and Figure 3, respectively. The humeral head is fixed on a shaft with low-friction bearings in the main frame, driven by a stepper motor through a range of 0° to 90° and back to 0° in the transverse plane with respect to a stationary fluid basket for mounting the glenoid component. The fluid basket is mounted in the center of a mobile face of a die set, which is fixed to the mainframe with load cells to measure the applied average load. The fluid basket, which allows

Figure 1 Motion and load profiles

for unambiguous positioning of the glenoid component as against the humeral head, contains lubricant. Individual control of the load is applied to this face by a pneumatic actuator mounted on the bottom face of the die set. When the load is applied, the face, together with

the fluid basket, moves vertically allowing for maintaining contact of the bearing surfaces of glenoid and humeral head.

The dynamically applied joint reaction forces have been synchronized to the physiologically representative joint abduction/adduction motions. To reproduce the motion profile shown in Figure 1, a stepper motor together with driver and controller with acceleration capability and control possibility were selected. To generate the complex physiologically correct loading (Figure 1) a double-acting pneumatic actuator together with a high precision, programmable pressure regulator was used. Both the rotation and load actuators are computer controlled by custom-made software programmed in LabView (National Instruments, Austin, Texas).

Figure 2 Schematic overview of the system

Figure 3 Shoulder Joint Wear Simulator

The software allows for continuously data acquisition of the frictional torque, applied load, rotation angle of the shaft and test environment temperature. To measure prosthetic joint friction, a custom-manufactured torque transducer was mounted between the shaft and stepper motor. Although there is no evidence, which confirms the importance of testing at body temperature of 37°C, the simulator is surrounded by thermo-isolated Plexiglas chamber. Inside the chamber a pre-adjusted temperature can be maintained by using a custom-manufactured air heater together with a thermocouple control system.

During the test 25% newborn calf serum with 0.1% sodium azide has been used as lubricant for simulation of the human joint synovial fluid. Because of evaporation of the water particles of the lubricant during the test, a passive replenishment system was utilized to maintain a constant level and concentration of lubricant in the glenoid fluid basket.

2.2 Wear and friction testing

In a preliminary test the wear performance of currently used glenoid and humeral components was tested in the shoulder wear simulator. The examined glenoid and humeral components were custom-manufactured from medical grade of UHMWPE and 316S, respectively. The head diameter was 44mm and the radius of glenoid articular surface curvature was 22mm. This makes the artificial joint conform. The thickness of the glenoid component was 6mm. The roughness of the components was $R_a=0.05 \mu\text{m}$. Because gamma radiation is most common as a sterilization method in industry, each UHMWPE component in this study has been treated by a commercially available gamma sterilization method with a radiation dose of 26.8 kGy.

After both glenoid and humeral head was fixed in anatomical positions in the simulator, the wear test has been started. The test ran for 2 millions cycles under physiological-correct load, which changed from 150N to 750N during each cycle. After the test was completed, the glenoid component was inspected for wear.

Wear rates were determined according to ASTM standard [2]. This test protocol uses weightloss method for evaluating wear properties for polymeric components used with shoulder replacement prosthesis under a dynamic load profile representative of the human shoulder joint during abduction. Every 200 000 cycles the glenoid component was removed

from the simulator, cleaned, dried and weighed in order to determine mass loss. A soak control component was also used to correct the measured mass loss due to fluid sorption. During the test this control component was placed in the temperature conditioned chamber soaked with the same type of the lubricant. Afterwards the actual net wear can be calculated. The actual net wear rate of the test specimen was calculated from the following equation:

$$W_n = (W_1 - W_2) + (S_2 - S_1) \quad (1)$$

where: W_1 = initial weight, W_2 = final weight, S_1 = initial weight control specimen, S_2 = final weight control specimen.

During the test the frictional torque, applied load, rotation angle of the shaft and test environment temperature were continuously recorded. This allows for calculation of friction factor.

2.3 Wear distribution and surface analysis

Before and after wear test, the articular surface of the glenoid component was scanned with accuracy of about $6\mu\text{m}$ using a laser scanner LDi (Laser Design Inc, Minneapolis). Based on these coordinate data sets the 3D geometrical models of articular surfaces were obtained using Geomagic software (Raindrop Geomagic Inc, Durham, NC).

Additionally, scanning electron microscopy (Balzers SCD040, JEOL, Peabody, MA) was used to examine the bearing surface of the glenoid component for structure, orientation of the wear tracks, roughness, deposits and even for stress-related gross microcracks. No attempt was made to measure wear of the stainless steel humeral head.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Validation of simulator

Before using the prototype simulator for actual material testing, initial preliminary test was done to validate the machine and the method of wear assessment. The test ran for 100,000 cycles under loads, which changed from 220N to 740N during each cycle. Good repeatability and accuracy performances of the motor and cylinder have been found.

3.2 Wear measurements

The gravimetric change of the glenoid component as a function of the number of cycles is shown in Figure 4. The conform 22mm UHMWPE glenoid component shows significant weightloss of about 75 mg after 2 millions cycles.

A gravimetric mass loss associated with fluid sorption of the polyethylene during the test was about $+7\mu\text{g}$ for the soak control specimen.

3.3 Friction factor

The frictional torque, applied load, rotation angle profiles were recorded during the preliminary test.

The frictional torque T is then converted into a friction factor f using the following equation:

$$f = \left| \frac{T}{R \cdot L} \right| \quad (2)$$

where: T = frictional torque between bearing surfaces; R [m] = humeral head radius; L [N] = applied load.

An example of the calculated friction factor f over one cycle has been shown in Figure 5. Over 2 mln cycles the minimum and maximum friction factors were found to be of about 0.019 (SD 0.03) and 0.142 (SD 0.02), respectively.

Figure 6 Top view of the glenoid bearing surface after testing

3.4 Wear distribution

A geometrical comparison of the worn and unworn surface of the glenoid component gives a radial deviation between the surfaces, which was referred as a wear depth.

The wear depth distribution for the tested glenoid component after 2 millions cycles is shown in Figure 6. The wear distribution shows maxima of the wear depth slightly inferio-lateral from the center portion. The maximum wear depth is of about 0.2 mm.

Figure 7 Scanning electron micrographs showing: a) unworn and worn regions together with scratches, b) scratches and ripples (note the horizontal oriented machining tracks), c) nodules next to the ripples, d) flakes, e) fibrillar pull-out, and f) microcracks.

3.5 Articular surface analysis

Upon a gross examination, the wear of polyethylene surface appeared. The wear track can be seen on the surface. Because a scanning electron microscopy allows to show fine details of

the worn surface, the glenoid component was examined using this technique for analyzing wear scar locations and a wear topography. The component was sputter-coated with a gold coating (20nm), placed in the SE microscope. Then, the articular surface was scanned at magnifications from x50 to x500. The obtained scanning electron micrographs of the surface were analyzed. It was found that at macroscopic level the worn surface has polished as well as scratched regions (Figure 7a). The linear scratches have a predominant inferio-superial direction (sliding direction). At microscopic level vertical oriented grooves and ripples together with horizontal oriented machining tracks were found (Figure 7b). From close-up image it can be seen that next to surface ripples nodules appeared (Figure 7c). Sometimes the nodules smeared to flakes (Figure 7d) or elongated fibrils (Figure 7e). Surface microcracks were also found (Figure 7f).

4. DISCUSSION

The developed wear simulator is capable for *in vitro* evaluating the friction and wear properties of combinations materials that are being considered for use as the bearing surfaces of human shoulder joint replacement under physiological load, motion, temperature and lubrication conditions. Moreover the friction factor between the articulating surfaces of the prosthetic components can be also calculated based on the measured friction torque. Because one million articulation cycles represents one year's implant service *in vivo* robust frame and accurate actuators units were needed to ensure good repeatability of the motion and load profiles over several million cycles each test period.

In this study, during 2 millions cycles of testing 22mm conform glenoid component a significant (75 mg), nonlinear loss of the weight was found. Assuming a polyethylene density of 0.946 mg/mm³ and 1 million cycles as one year *in vivo* component use, the calculated volumetric wear rate is of about 40 mm³/yr. Unfortunately, the obtained wear rate cannot be validated because no similar shoulder simulators studies have been reported yet, which investigate the wear rate in total shoulder replacements. Also the retrievals analyses, which have been published [1,7], don't show any quantitative data describing wear. However, the obtained wear rate is within the average value that has been observed clinically in hip arthroplasty (90± 44mm³/yr) [10].

Based on measured friction torque the friction factor between the articulating surfaces of the prosthetic components under a newborn calf serum lubrication conditions was calculated. The obtained maximum friction factor of about 0.14 is about two times higher than has been found in metal-on-plastic hip prostheses [6].

The 3D-Laser Scan techniques used in this study has proved to be useful measuring instruments for evaluation of glenoid component wear depth and wear distribution. The maximum wear depth of the scratched regions was found to be of about 0.2 mm. However, the real maximum wear depth is smaller (about 0.1 mm) because these deep scratches were obtained as result of a third body wear process caused by dried particles of the serum. Wear distribution picture shows more wear in inferior region of glenoid surface what is in agreement with the results of the retrieval components analysis [5].

The SEM surface analysis shows significant wear tracks worn away by initial shearing perpendicular to the original machining tracks. Stretched formations of deformed PE and deep scratches were determined within the inferio-central region of the glenoid surface. These damage modes are similar to the modes, which were found in the studies of retrieval glenoid components [5].

5. CONCLUSIONS

A one-station shoulder wear simulator was developed in this study. It allows for *in vitro* evaluating the friction and wear properties of prosthetic components of the total shoulder replacement under physiological load/motion/lubrication conditions. Through the preliminary wear test of the currently used glenoid component, the device proved effectiveness at reproducing the desired motions and loads, and initiating wear. The significant abrasive and

adhesive wear of the polyethylene surface of the component, which has been found, might result in generation of wear debris, thus cause implant loosening.

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